

PHRASEOLOGICAL EQUIVALENTS THAT CHARACTERIZE EMOTIONS IN THE TATAR, GERMAN, AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract

In the article it is researched phraseological units of the Tatar, German, English languages which characterized the emotions of people. The authors studied phraseological units which reflect the emotional and mental state of a person, such as: fear, grief, joy, sadness. The authors researched full equivalents of the phraseological units of the Tatar, German, English languages to analyzed cross-cultural influence, psychological conditions of a person which can be expressed the same way with the same language words, or, on the contrary when the phraseological units reflect the difference in culture, mentality. The object of the research is phraseological units that characterize the emotional state of a person. The subject of the study is phraseological units that have full equivalents in three languages: Tatar, German, and English. The scientific novelty of the study consists of characterizing the mental state of a person, having a complete analogy in two genetically related languages Germanic languages of the Indi-European family and an unrelated Turkic speaking group. The authors analyzed the works of the leading linguists and studied dictionaries of phraseological units and it was found out that there were many phraseological units with the same meaning and the same words. The phraseological units of the Tatar language have full equivalents due to direct translation them from the Russian language. However, the phraseological units in the Tatar language have some grammar peculiarities as the language belongs to other family groups. The authors think that the full equivalents reflect the emotions which are subsistent to a human being.

Keywords: linguistics, phraseological units, Tatar, German, English, language, language system, equivalents.

1 INTRODUCTION

The inner world of a person, his relationship with the environment attracts the attention of not only philosophers, psychologists, teachers, but also linguists. Considering the human factor in a language, the development of the anthropocentric paradigm of linguistics has been determined, which has become a separate field in linguistics. Humanity has a single biological nature, therefore, such a category as the mental and emotional state of a person is universal. Native speakers of different languages inherit, along with their national and cultural uniqueness, universal values and properties, thanks to which communication and mutual understanding between representatives of cultures makes the comparison possible. Comparative research of linguistic phenomena in the field of phraseology attracts the attention of linguists due to the importance of identifying common and specific features at the phraseological level of several languages. The identification of areas of contact between different languages allows us to identify common characteristics of the history, culture, and psychology of various language communities. Knowledge of the phraseological units of the language allows us to understand the mentality of the nation.

Thus, the object of our research is phraseological units (PhU) that characterize the emotional states of a person. The subject of the study is the phraseological units that have full equivalences in three languages: Tatar, German, and English.

The purpose of our research is a comprehensive study and identification of phraseological units that have full equivalences in three languages, expressing such mental states of a person as joy, anxiety and fear, surprise, anger affect, states of discomfort, emotional uplift, based on the material of the Tatar, German and English languages.

The relevance of the study is primarily determined by the growth of intercultural contacts. It is relevant to involve the phraseological units of the Tatar, German, and English languages in the field with the new psycholinguistic direction in comparative linguistics. The interaction of two languages of the Germanic group and one language of the Turkic group is attractive and relevant in the conditions of expanding the boundaries of communication.

The scientific novelty of the study is that it is studied the meaning and the structure phraseological units characterizing the emotional states of a person which are full equivalence in two genetically related and one unrelated language with the involvement of data from analytical psychology and the psychology of states.

The theoretical significance lies in the further development of the problem of phraseological units, which is a complex of multi-tiered formation.

2. METHODS

Phraseological units have been studied by many well-known linguists as A. V. Kunin, V.V. Vinogradov, A.A. Shakhmatov, E.F. Arsentieva [3],[4]. Anthropocentric PhU became the object of research in the works of N.N. Amosova [2], G.H. Akhunzyanov [1], N.F. L.E. Blinovich [5], Molostova (2000), G. Z. Darzamanova (2002), A. R. Zalyaleeva (2003), G. A. Bagautdinova (2007). In the works E.F. Arsentieva studied PhUs characterizing the intellectual and thinking abilities of a person [4]. A.D. Reichstein studied phraseological units of the German language [10]. In comparison, the phraseological units expressing negative states were studied on the example of the Russian and German languages by R.V. Gataullina [7], [8], [9]. N. M. Dotsenko (1985) and N. M. Kurikalova (1985) studied the structure of the phrase semantic field of the internal state and the phenomena of the inner life of a person. G. A. Bagautdinova (1985), and F.S. Safina researched phraseological means of subjective assessment of personality [11]. The leading method of the research is the study of theoretical and methodological literature on this theme. The authors used the following groups of the methods which helped in this research:

- a descriptive method for observation and classification of the material;
- a system-oriented analysis of literature and the stated topic;
- an analysis of dictionaries of phraseological units and idioms in the Tatar, German and English languages.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Phraseological equivalents make up the main group of interlanguage correspondences of phraseological units (PhU) expressing a person's mental states in the Tatar, German and English languages. There are few

full equivalents in three languages. It is due to the difference in language systems. Firstly, the connection of words does not occur according to one type: the word order is different, there are no case endings and personal forms of the verb in the Tatar, German and English languages. In the Tatar language there is a suffix formation of words, which distinguishes it from two European languages (German and English). The next difference between the Tatar language and two European languages is the absence of prepositions and categories of gender, type, and articles. In the German language, on the contrary, there is a strict word order in a sentence. Considering the full phraseological equivalents in the compared languages, it should be noted that when the significative-denotative macro component coincides, the meanings and connotations may differ not only in the component composition, but also in the structural and grammatical organization. They may coincide or have differences in the figurative basis. Despite the wide range of not existing types of complete analogs, it has been found out some full equivalents in these languages and it is possible to unit them in one group by a common property, namely, the identity of the significative-denotative component of the phraseological meaning.

As an example, we can cite phraseological units in the three comparative languages that characterize a bad mood, irritability, a bad spirit, distemper:

- **сул ягы белән торган /тору** (Tatar PhU);
- **mit dem linken /verkehrten Bein (zuerst) aufstehen** (German PhU);
- **get out of bed on the wrong side /way, rise /get up on the wrong side** (English PhU).

It is an example of the complete equivalence of PhU in the comparative languages which can be cited with the word "get out", "wrong side", "wrong leg". This PhU refers to full analogues, due to small differences in imagery, however, there are differences in the number of components, the order of words, for example in the German and English languages there are changeable components:

in German PhU – "**linken /verkehrten Bein**",

in English PhU "**wrong side /way**",

in Tatar PhU, there aren't changeable components in "**sul yag(s)**", just wrong side. In German and English, in this example, there is an optional component "zuerst"(Gr) "out of bed"(En). This PhU differs in their stylistic affiliation. The figurative basis for the rethinking was a superstitious belief, according to which it was believed that the day would be successful if you get out of bed with the right leg /right side.

2. Next full equivalent PhU in three comparative languages is "to **tremble like a leaf**". It expresses "fear/ alarm". This PhU could be borrowed from European languages into Russian, and then directly translated by the Tatars. There is also the PhU "tremble like an aspen leaf" in the Russian language. However, this PhU has differences in their component composition, for example, in the Tatar and English PhU there are changeable components:

- сак **яфрагы** кебек калтырый/ **куян**_(hare) кебек калтырый (Tatar PhU);
- zittern wie **Espenlaub** (German PhU);
- tremble/ shake/ quiver like an **apen leaf** (English PhU).

The Tatar people also use the word "kuyan "(hare in Tatar) when they want to express fear which is very close to the Russian equivalent. In the English and German languages we see the grammar structure of this PhU **V+comp+N**, in the Tatar language the Grammar structure is **N+comp+V**. But in all comparative languages we find the comparative component: "in the Tatar language" **kebek**", in German "**wie**", in English "**like**"; there is also a similarity in imagery "aspen leaf" in all compared languages. The figurative basis for the rethinking was the psychophysiological sensation, which reflexes reaction of the body. The strong emotional state as fear is reflected with trembling of the muscles of a body. When we have fear we breathe hard, we have strong heart strokes, we tremble etc.

3. There are some full equivalents of PhUs which connected with the parts of the body. Psychologists have noticed the fact that the behavior of an individual allows us to distinguish two opposite poles in it "good and evil". The following example of a complete equivalence of PhU in three languages is connected with the word "hair", for example "blush to the roots of (one's) hair", which means confusion, shame, embarrassment, attainment etc.

- чәч** төбенә кадәр кызару (Tatar PhU);

-bis in die **Haarswurzeln** erröten (German PhU);

-**blush /flush /redden** to the **roots of (one`s) hair** (English PhU).

But this PhU has some small differences in imagery, the significative-denotative and connotative components of phraseological meaning are characterized by belonging to interstitial phraseological units. There are differences in the components of the PhU "chach toplare" (hair roots in Tatar), "die Haarswurzeln" (hair roots in German), but there are changeable components in the English PhU as "blush", "flush", "redden". There is no grammar difference in the structure in this PhU: N+V. The imagery of these PhU is based on a hyperbolized description of psychophysiological reactions, such as facial redness, which is universal for all people.

There are some synonyms to the previous PhU meaning a strong psychological stress as fear, for example "the soul has gone to the heels".

- **йөрәк** аска /үкчәгә төшәп китте /китү (Tatar PhU) (heart/boots swoop down);
- **das Herz** fällt (j-m) in die Hosen (German PhU) (heart falls in the trousers);
- **(one`s) heart** sank into (one`s) boots / shoes (English PhU).

This PhU differs at the level of stylistic affiliation, structural and grammatical organization, but it has a similar imagery in the hyperonization of the description of the work of the heart. There are differences in the component composition: in German "in die Hosen" (in trousers), in English there are changeable components "into (one's) boots /in boots/into (one's) shoes "(in shoes), in Tatar - "aska "(down)," ukcheg "(boots), but they have the same common component 'heart - yorak (Tatar), das Herz (German), heart (English).

4. Next PhU of full equivalent in three coparative languages means some strangeness in behavior of a human being, for example "have a screw loose".

- **шөрөбе какшаган /какшый башлаган** (Tatar PhU);
- **in (seinem) Kopf ist eine Schraube los /locker** (German PhU);
- **have a tile loose** (English PhU).

They have the same significative-denotative component of the meaning, they belong to colloquial units, but there are also differences in imagery, due to the presence of changeable components such as : "kakshagan", "kakshy bashlagan" ('tremble in Tatar'), "los", "locker" - "loose" in German; "shoreb"(screw in Tatar),"Schraube"(screw' in German) , there is an optional components "in (seinem) Kopf" ('in the head in German). The common semantic denominator for these PhU is 'screw'. The imagery is based on the description of an unreal situation, or problem with the head: the screws / nuts in the head are loosened /began to loosen /fell out). PhU in these languages are characterized by a negative assessment of what is happening. PhU in the German and English languages have a sense of neglectation, In the PhU in the Tatar language we feel more irony.

5. There are some full equivalent PhUs expressing 'surprise' with one common component "the eyes" in the Tatar, German, and English languages.

- **күз(е) маңгаена мен(гән)** (Tatar PhU) (the eye went to the forehead);
- **(j-m) fallen die Augen aus dem Kopf** (German PhU) (eyes fell out of the head);
- **(one's) eyes stand / pop out of (one's) head** (English PhU).

However, the lexeme "kuz(e)" ('eye') is used in the singular in the Tatar language. In the English language PhU have changeable components "stand out of" and "popped out of". This PhU is characterized by similar imagery, which is based on a hyperbolized description of human face expressions.

There are some more examples of full equivalents PhUs expressing negative states of a human being as 'fear, terror', but with some peculiarities. For example,

a) with a common semantic substitute "**heart**":

- **йөрәк** туктар хәлгә житү (Tatar) (heart almost stopped);

- (j-m) schien **das Herz** stillzustehen (German) (it seemed that the heart almost stopped);
- (one's) **heart** stood still (English).

b) full equivalent but different in grammar structure with a common word “**blood**” meaning “the blood runs cold in the veins”, e.g.

- **кан өши** (Tatar PhU) (blood becomes cold);
- **das Blut** erstarrt /stockt /gefriert /gerinnt (j-m) in den Adern (German PhU);
- (one`s) **blood** turned to ice (English PhU).

c) with the common word “**the hair**”, which used to express fear (terror):

- чәч үрә торды (‘chach’ ‘hair’) (Tatar PhUs);
- (j-m) stehen **die Haare** zu Berge (German PhU);
- one's **hair** stands on end (English PhU).

d). with the word “shadow”, “reflection”. the PhU means “to be afraid of your own shadow”. English PhU has two verbs to show fear.

- үз шәүләңнән курку (‘shadow’) (Tatar PhU);
- den eigenen **Schatten** fürchten “Shatten”(‘shadow’) (German PhU);
- be afraid /frightened of one`s own **shadow** (English PhU).

e) with the word “the God”, the PU means to be afraid of God:

- **ходайдан** курку “hodai”, “God” (Tatar PhU);
- (j-m) mit (**Gottes**) Strafe drohen, (Gott) (German PhU);
- keep smb in **God's** fear, put the fear of God into (smb) (English PhU). However, the English people use 2 verbs “keep” and “put” .

f) with the common word “**fire**” is “to be afraid like fire”, for example:

- **уттан** курыккан кебек курку (‘utt’ fire (TatarPhU);
- (etw) wie **das Feuer** fürchten “Feuer” fire (German PhU);
- fear (smb/ smth) like **fire** /plague (English PhU). The English people can use 2 words ‘fire’ and ‘plague’.

6. The PhUs which are used to express anxiety, meaning “the soul is not in its place” has some defenses in words and grammatical structure:

- үзеңне-үзең кая кая куярга белмәү (‘one cannot find himself a place’ (Tatar));
- (j-d) kann keine Ruhe finden, (‘Ruhe’ calm” (German);
- be not oneself (English)

7. Full equivalents are the PhUs which describe astonishment with the word “eye”, where the common semantic denominator is “making big round eyes”

- **күзләрен** шар ясау (Tatar PhU);
- **Augen** machen /glotzen (German PhU);
- to bat an **eyelash**; to raise one **eyebrow**. In English it used extra words to express this emotion, not just “eyes”.

8. Full equivalents PhUs with the common semantic denominator “like thunder struck”, e.g:

- **яшен** суккандай булу (Tatar PhU);
- wie vom **Donner /Blitz** gerührt /getroffen sein (‘Donner/Blitz’ thunder/ lightning (German PhU);

- hit with **thunder** (English). These are the examples with the same meaning, but with grammar peculiarities. In German language we find simile "wie".

9. The full equivalents have been also found in the in PhU which reflect some physiological processes of a human being, for example "**breathtaking**":

- **улыш** кабу /кысылу (Tatar PhU)
- etw. **nimmt /versetzt /verschlagt** (j-m) **den Atem** (German PhU)
- (it) takes (one`s) **breath** away (English PhU)

This example reflects psychophysiological reactions and pantomimic of a human being which is the same and doesn't depend on cultural peculiarities. This PhU has a common component "breath". However there are some changeable components in German language, like as "nimmt (takes) /versetzt "(displaces) /verschlagt (capture) "which couldn't be found in the Tatar and English languages. These examples show some more differences: in imagery, the significative-denotative and connotative components of phraseological meaning, the level of the structural and grammatical organization of PhU. In the German and English PhU there are mutable pronouns "one's" - "someone's" and "j-m"; in the Tatar language we don't have the same components due to absence of the gender category.

6. It has been found PhUs which have some animals parts of the body to describe human feelings as depression , for example:

- **койрыкны** бот арасына кыстыру (Tatar PhU);
- **den Schwanz** zwischen die Beine einziehen (German PhU);
- **(one s) tail** is between (one s) legs, get /have (one`s) **tail** down (English PhU).

We use the word "tail" in PhU to express depression in three comparative languages. However, these PhUs have some differences at the level of structural and grammatical organization, and they also differ in component composition, but stylistic affiliation of PhU has a common component "tail", it has a similar imagery.

II. Full Equivalents Expressing depression/ despair.

For example, a) "banging your head against the wall";

- **башны** ташка опу (TatarPhU);
- mit **dem Kopf** gegen die Wand rennen (GermanPhU);
- run (one's) **head** into a brick / stone / wall (English PhU).

b) full equivalent are the PhUs which character sadness "a stone on the heart/ soul"

- **йөрәктә** авырташ кебек булу /таш булып утыру (Tatar PhU);
- (j-m) lastet etwas schwer auf **dem Herzen** (German PhU);
- a weight lies heavy on (one's) **heart** (English PhU).

c) It was found full equivalents which characterized grief, for example " breaking the heart":

- **жанны** /**йөрәкне** /бәгерне өзү (Tatar PhU);
- die Seele /**das Herz** zerreißen (German PhU);
- break (one's) **heart** (English PhU).

The second example:

- **йөрәк** парә-парә килү (Tatar PhU);
- (etw) schneidet (j-m) **das Herz** (German PhU);
- make (smb's) **heart** bleed (English PhU)
-

III. Full Equivalents Expressing Positive Feelings.

There were examples of full equivalents in three comparative languages which express negative emotional states of people. The authors also studied some PhUs which express positive emotions as joy, happiness, for example, "jump to the ceiling for joy" which describes an affective form of joy, e.g:

- **шатлыктан кая басарга белмәү** (Tatar PhU);
- **vor Freude bis an die Decker springen** (German PhU);
- **jump for joy / leap for joy/ jump over the moon** (English PhU).

This PhU has differences in imagery: we use the word "joy" in three languages but in the Tatar language the direct translation is "not to know where to step from joy"; in German language the direct translation is "jump up to the ceiling", in, connotative macro-component. The English equivalent has synonyms.

b) full equivalents meaning relief and joy, e.g. with the word "**breath**"

- **жиңел сулап** кую ('jengel' breath) (take a breath) (Tatar PhU);
- **Atem holen** ('Atem' breath) (German PhU);
- take a deep **breath** of joy (English PhU).

c) PhUs, where the common semantic denominator is "**to be at the top of heaven**"

- **йөрәк сикереп чыгар хәлгә житү** (Tatar PhU);
- (sich) (wie) im siebten /siebenten **Himmel** fühlen (German PhU);
- in (the) **seventh heaven** (English PhU)

4. CONCLUSION

After analyzing full equivalents of PhUs in three comparative languages which describe the emotional states of a person, we concluded that a significant part of the PhUs in the Tatar, German and English languages are full equivalents.

There are some reasons. Firstly, PhUs describe a person's psychological states which are the same and don't depend on cultural peculiarities. People have the same reaction to fear, depression, joy, happiness. Psychophysiological changes in the human body and emotional experiences are universal for all people, in any language.

However, there are also some peculiarities in grammar structure, in number of synonyms, collocations, and stylistic peculiarities as for example in the Tatar language we feel more irony than in the English and the German languages.

This topic is of interest to both psychologists and linguists, as it pursues the goal of finding translation correspondences for languages that have phraseological equivalents and polychrome equivalents in another language.

Full phraseological equivalents include multilingual verbs that coincide in the significative-denotative macro component of the meaning. Differences are observed in the component composition, structural and grammatical organization, imagery, functional and stylistic belonging of words, in the emotional meanings of connotations.

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